

Enviro-economic synthesis of some phthalimide derivatives using microwave irradiation

Chetna Ameta, Rakshit Ameta^a, Urvashi Tiwari, P. B. Punjabi and Suresh C. Ameta*

Microwave Chemistry Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Mohanlal Sukhadia University,
Udaipur-313 001, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : ameta_sc@yahoo.com

^aDepartment of Pure and Applied Chemistry, University of Kota, Kota-324 005, Rajasthan, India

Manuscript received 14 June 2010, accepted 28 October 2010

Abstract : An environmentally benign, efficient and facile route is developed for the preparation of phthalimide derivatives by using LiBr as a catalyst under solvent free condition and microwave exposure. In comparison to conventional synthesis involving tedious workup, excessive use of solvent and extra labour for separation and purification of compounds, the present method indicates operational simplicity, shorter reaction time and higher yields which can prove this procedure as a useful alternative for the synthesis of heterocycles. The potent antimicrobial effects of the synthesized compounds were investigated.

Keywords : Phthalimide, LiBr, solvent free condition, microwave exposure.

Introduction

MAOS¹ (Microwave Assisted Organic Synthesis) strategies offer feasible solutions as their benefits are manifold : it frequently leads to dramatically reduction in reaction time, higher yields, cleaner reaction profiles and above all, eco-friendliness. One fact that a “yes or no answer” for a particular chemical transformation can often be obtained within 5 to 10 min (as compared to several hours in conventional protocol) has contributed significantly to the acceptance of microwave chemistry both; in industry and academia^{2,3}. In conventional synthesis expensive and toxic solvents are used which are hazardous and cause severe health problems. On the other hand, solvent free conditions offer green chemical route for synthesis of organic compounds⁴⁻⁷. Condensation reactions have been a subject of considerable interest and to effect this condensation efficiently, large number of catalyst have been explored^{8,9}, e.g. sodium acetate in glacial acetic acid, piperidinium benzoate in refluxing toluene, zeolite, tetra butyl ammonium bromide, refluxing reactants in toluene at 110 °C for 3 days, etc. These processes are not much facile as they require long reaction times, high temperature and even than the products are obtained in low yields. LiBr¹⁰⁻¹³ is a flexible, mild, re-

cyclable, efficient and inexpensive reagent, which can potentially replace solvents and conventional corrosive acids in many of their applications¹⁴⁻¹⁷.

In view of this, it was planned to apply these new methodologies (MW, solvent free conditions, LiBr) in present research work. This approach offers several advantages such as shorter reaction times, good yields, low cost, recycling of the catalyst, and simple workup. Phthalimide derivatives are found to be endowed with potential biological activities such as antifungal¹⁸, hypolipidemic^{19,20}, antibacterial^{21,22}, anticonvulsant^{23,24}, antimicrobial^{25,26}, antitumor^{27,28} activities and many others.

Thus the coupling of this MW enhanced synthesis with solvent free conditions and LiBr is expected to afford an environmentally benign synthesis of some biological active compounds.

Results and discussion

2-(Hydroxymethyl)-1*H*-isoindole-1,3(2*H*)-dione (1) was synthesized by LiBr catalyzed addition of formaldehyde on phthalimide under solvent free condition and microwave exposure. The structure of (1) was confirmed by the IR bands at 3442 cm⁻¹ due to hydroxy group. It is

supported by the presence of a broad singlet of 1 OH protons in the region of 5.12 ppm in ^1H NMR. The compound (1) was treated with ethyl 4-methylbenzoate in the presence of LiBr to give ethyl 3-[(1,3-dioxo-1,3-dihydro-2*H*-isoindol-2-yl)methyl]-4-methylbenzoate (2). The structure of compound (2) was confirmed by the disappearance of OH stretch in the region of 3442 cm^{-1} in IR spectrum and appearance of an additional band at 1180 cm^{-1} due to C–O–C stretch and 1723 cm^{-1} due to C=O stretch of ester moiety. ^1H NMR spectrum of (2) shows the appearance of a quartet due to two protons (CH_2) at 4.02 ppm and triplet due to three protons (CH_3) at 2.09 ppm of the ester moiety. Compound (2) was easily condensed with 4-aminoacetophenone in the presence of basic alumina to furnish *N*-(4-acetylphenyl)-3-[(1,3-dioxo-1,3-dihydro-2*H*-isoindol-2-yl)methyl]-4-methylbenzamide (3).

The IR spectrum of compound (3) shows the appearance of NH stretch at 3335 cm^{-1} , CH_3 stretch at 1158 cm^{-1} and disappearance of a band at 1180 cm^{-1} due to C–O–C stretch and 1723 cm^{-1} due to C=O stretch of ester moiety. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound was characterized by the lack of a quartet of two protons (CH_2), triplet

of three protons (CH_3) of ester moiety and the presence of a singlet of 1 NH proton at 5.70 ppm.

Compound (3) undergoes condensation with various aromatic aldehydes in the presence of LiBr to give *N*-{4-(3-(substituted phenyl)prop-2-enoyl)phenyl}-3-(1,3-dioxo-1,3-dihydro-2*H*-isoindol-2-yl)methyl]-4-methylbenzamide (4a-j). The formation of compounds (4a-j) was confirmed by the disappearance of a signal of CH_3 group in compounds (3) due to condensation with substituted benzaldehydes and appearance of a new singlet in the region of 4.71–3.60 ppm due to arylidene proton ($=\text{CH-Ar}$) of chalcone moiety.

Antimicrobial activity :

Three compounds were screened *in vitro* for their antimicrobial activities against four strains of bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) and two strains of fungi (*Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Candida albicans*) using the disc diffusion method. Commercial antibacterial ciprofloxacin and antifungal fluconazole were also screened under similar conditions for comparison. The results have been tabulated in the form of inhibition zones and activity index in Table 2.

Table 1. Physical data of synthesized compounds

a = Conventional, b = Microwave + Solvent, c = Microwave + LiBr (solvent free) under microwave irradiation

Compd.	Ar	Molecular formula	Molecular weight	M.p. (°C)	Yield ^a (%) (Time) (h)	Yield ^b (%) (Time) (min)	Yield ^c (%) (Time) (min)
1	-	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{NO}_3$	177	135–136	66 [2]	69 [3]	76 [2]
2	-	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_4$	323	120–122	61 [7]	70 [5]	78 [5]
3	-	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$	456	99–100	65 [4]	86 [3.30]	80 [3]
4a	$-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$	$\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$	500	120–121	66 [12]	69 [5.30]	76 [5]
4b	$4\text{-NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4^-$	$\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_3\text{O}_6$	545	180–181	65 [12]	86 [5.30]	80 [5]
4c	$2\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4^-$	$\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$	534	180–181	68 [12]	72 [5.30]	89 [5]
4d	$3\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4^-$	$\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$	534	176–177	73 [12]	75 [5.30]	87 [5]
4e	$2\text{-OHC}_6\text{H}_4^-$	$\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$	516	165–166	70 [12]	76 [5.30]	87 [5]

Table-1 (contd)

4f	3-OHC ₆ H ₄ -	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₅	516	178-179	68 [12]	72 [5 30]	86 [5]
4g	4-FC ₆ H ₄ -	C ₃₂ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₄ F	518	175-176	69 [12]	77 [5 30]	88 [5]
4h	2-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₃₃ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₅	530	138-139	68 [12]	70 [5 30]	80 [5]
4i	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₃₃ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₅	530	142-143	68 [12]	70 [5 30]	86 [5]
4j		C ₃₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₅	490	158-159	79 [12]	82 [5 30]	90 [5]

Table 2. Antimicrobial activities of some synthesized compounds (500 ppm)

Compd	Antifungal activity (Activity index)		Antibacterial activity (Activity index)			
	<i>A. fumigatus</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>
4a	28	27 (0 90)	29 (0 80)	20 (0 62)	16 (0 40)	24 (0 66)
4i	24	22 (0 73)	21 (0 58)	17 (0 53)	14 (0 35)	21 (0 58)
4j	29	20 (0 66)	23 (0 63)	22 (0 68)	10 (0 25)	20 (0 55)
C ₁	0	30	-	-	-	-
C ₂	-	-	36	32	40	36

^aActivity index = Inhibition area of the sample/inhibition area of the standard

Standard · C₁ = Fluconazole, C₂ = Ciprofloxacin

The results revealed that all tested compounds exhibit moderate to strong activity against both fungi and *E. coli*. Compounds **4(a)**, **4(i)** and **4(j)** show considerable potency against *A. fumigatus* while against *C. albicans*, they are moderately active. Similarly, compounds **4(a)**, **4(i)** and **4(j)** were found to show strong activity against *K. pneumoniae* and *B. subtilis* while against *P. aeruginosa*, they exhibited least activity.

Experimental

Apparatus :

All reactions were carried out in a domestic microwave oven (Kenstar, Model : OM-26 EGO). Melting points are uncorrected and determined in open capillaries. Reactions were monitored by thin layer chromatography using silica gel-G as adsorbent using ethyl acetate : *n*-hexane (7 : 3) as eluent and products were detected by iodine vapors. IR spectra (KBr pellets) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 1800 (FTIR) spectrometer. ¹H NMR spectra

(DMSO-*d*₆) were taken on a Bruker DRX spectrometer (300 MHz, FT NMR) using TMS as internal standard and chemical shift were expressed in δ. Mass spectra were taken on a Jeol SX-102/PA-6000 (EI) spectrometer and elemental analysis was carried out on C, H, N analyzer (Elemental Vario Carlo Alba 1108). The results were found to be in good agreement with the calculated values (±0.2%). The starting compounds were prepared according to reported method.

Microwave induced synthesis of 2-(hydroxymethyl)-1*H*-isoindole-1,3-(2*H*)-dione (1) :

A mixture of phthalimide (0.01 mol), formaldehyde (0.01 mol) and LiBr (10 mol%) was mixed with a glass rod and placed in small conical flask at room temperature. The mixture was then exposed to microwave radiations at 80% power for 2-3 min. After completion of reaction (monitored by TLC), the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature. 15 mL of water was then added to reaction mixture and it was stirred for 5 min.

- Ar
- a = -C₆H₅
 - b = 4-NO₂C₆H₄·
 - c = 2-ClC₆H₄·
 - d = 3-ClC₆H₄·
 - e = 2-OHC₆H₄·
 - f = 3-OHC₆H₄·
 - g = 4-FC₆H₄·
 - h = 2-OCH₃C₆H₄·
 - i = 4-OCH₃C₆H₄·
 - j =

The solid thus obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol to yield compound (1) (Found : C, 59.05; H, 3.46; N, 7.04. Calcd. for C₉H₇NO₃ : C, 61.02; H, 3.98; N, 7.91%); IR (KBr cm⁻¹) : 3020 (C-H str., Ar-H), 3442 (OH str.), 2887 (CH₂ str.), 1774, 1762 (C=O cyclic amide str.), 1424 (C-N str.) and 1601 (C=C str.); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 4.21 (2H, s, CH₂), 5.12 (1H, broad, OH) and 7.23–8.30 (4H, m, Ar-H).

Conventional synthesis of 2-(hydroxymethyl)-1H-isoindole-1,3-(2H)-dione (1) :

About (0.01 mol) of phthalimide and formaldehyde (0.01 mol) were heated together in an oil bath for 2 h.

Subsequently, the content was cooled and dilute HCl (50 mL) was added slowly with constant stirring. A solid was separated out, which is crystallized from ethanol to yield compound (1).

Microwave induced synthesis of ethyl 3-[(1,3-dioxo-1,1-dihydro-2H-isoindol-2-yl)methyl]-4-methylbenzoate (2) :

Compound (1) (0.01 mol), ethyl 4-methylbenzoate (0.01 mol) and LiBr (10 mol%) was placed in a small conical flask and mixed with a glass rod at room temperature. The mixture was then exposed to microwave radiations at 60% power for 3–4 min. After completion of reaction (monitored by TLC), the reaction mixture

was cooled to room temperature. 15 mL of water was then added to reaction mixture and it was stirred for 5 min. The solid thus obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol to afford compound **2** (Found : C, 59.05; H, 3.46; N, 7.04. Calcd. for C₉H₇NO₃ : C, 61.02; H, 3.98; N, 7.91%); IR (KBr cm⁻¹) : 3032 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2871 (CH₂ str.), 1779, 1767 (C=O cyclic amide str.), 1180 (C-O-C str.), 2915 (CH₃ str.), 1723 (C=O of ester str.), 1433 (C-N str.) and 1605 (C=C str.); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 4.16 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.01 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.02 (2H, q, O-CH₂-CH₃), 2.09 (3H, t, O-CH₂-CH₃) and 7.16–8.25 (7H, m, Ar-H).

Conventional synthesis of ethyl 3-[(1,3-dioxo-1,3-dihydro-2H-isoindol-2-yl)methyl]-4-methylbenzoate (2) :

Compound **(1)** (0.01 mol), ethyl 4-methylbenzoate (0.01 mol) and fused CH₃COONa (0.5 g) in acetic acid (10 mL) was refluxed for about 7 h on a heating mantle. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into ice cold water. The solid separated was filtered off and recrystallized from ethanol to obtain compounds **(2)**.

Microwave induced synthesis of N-(4-acetylphenyl)-3-[(1,3-dioxo-1,3-dihydro-2H-isoindol-2-yl)methyl]-4-methylbenzamide (3) :

Compound **(2)** (0.01 mol), 4-aminoacetophenone (0.01 mol) and basic alumina (2 g) were mixed with mortar-pestle and placed in a small conical flask at room temperature. The mixture was then exposed to microwave radiations at 50% power for 3–3.30 min. After completion of reaction (monitored by TLC), the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature. Then dichloromethane (20 mL) was added and the mixture was stirred for 5 min, filtered, evaporated and recrystallized from ethanol to afford compound **(3)** (Found : C, 59.05; H, 3.46; N, 7.04. Calcd. for C₉H₇NO₃ : C, 61.02; H, 3.98; N, 7.91%); IR (KBr cm⁻¹) : 3027 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2801 (CH₂ str.), 1768, 1698 (C=O cyclic amide str.), 3335 (NH str.), 1158 (CH₃ str.), 1665 (C=O str.), 1429 (C-N str.) and 1619 (C=C str.); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 4.16 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.01 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.70 (1H, s, NH), 2.02 (3H, s, O=C-CH₃) and 7.08–8.19 (11H, m, Ar-H).

Conventional synthesis of N-(4-acetylphenyl)-3-[(1,3-

dioxo-1,3-dihydro-2H-isoindol-2-yl)methyl]-4-methylbenzamide (3) :

Compound **(2)** (0.01 mol), 4-aminoacetophenone (0.01 mol) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (2.2 g) in carbon tetrachloride (100 mL) was refluxed for 4 h on a water-bath. The solvent was distilled off and the separated solid was crystallized from ethanol.

Microwave induced synthesis of N-{4-[3-phenylprop-2-enoyl]phenyl}-3-[(1,3-dioxo-1,3-dihydro-2H-isoindol-2-yl)methyl]-4-methylbenzamide (4a) :

Compound **(3)** (0.01 mol), benzaldehydes (0.01 mol) and LiBr (10 mol%) was placed in a small conical flask and mixed with a glass rod at room temperature. The mixture was then exposed to microwave radiations at 60% power for 5–5.30 min. After completion of reaction (monitored by TLC), the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature. 15 mL of water was then added to reaction mixture and it was stirred for 5 min. The solid thus obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol to afford compound **4(a)** (Found : C, 70.12; H, 4.01; N, 4.25. Calcd. for C₃₂H₂₄N₂O₄ : C, 76.78; H, 4.83; N, 5.60%); IR (KBr cm⁻¹) : 3027 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2412 (CH₂ str.), 1771, 1722 (C=O cyclic amide str.), 3332 (NH str.), 1702 (C=O str.), 1412 (C-N str.) and 1597 (C=C str.); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 4.16 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.73 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.15 (1H, s, NH), 7.36 (1H, d, CH), 7.25 (1H, d, CH) and 7.46–8.31 (15H, m, Ar-H).

N-{4-[3-(4-Nitrophenyl)prop-2-enoyl]phenyl}-3-[(1,3-dioxo-1,3-dihydro-2H-isoindol-2-yl)methyl]-4-methylbenzamide (4b) : Found : C, 68.32; H, 3.46; N, 6.35. Calcd. for C₃₂H₂₃N₃O₆ : C, 70.45; H, 4.25; N, 7.70%; IR (KBr cm⁻¹) : 3021 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2401 (CH₂ str.), 1778, 1725 (C=O cyclic amide str.), 3302 (NH str.), 1551, 1412 (Ar-NO₂ str.), 1619 (C=O str.), 1432 (C-N str.) and 1568 (C=C str.); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 4.12 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.51 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.31 (1H, s, NH), 7.56 (1H, d, CH), 7.45 (1H, d, CH) and 7.02–8.15 (15H, m, Ar-H).

N-{4-[3-(2-Chlorophenyl)prop-2-enoyl]phenyl}-3-[(1,3-dioxo-1,3-dihydro-2H-isoindol-2-yl)methyl]-4-methylbenzamide (4c) : Found : C, 70.02; H, 3.26; N, 4.15. Calcd. for C₃₂H₂₃N₂O₄Cl : C, 71.84; H, 4.33; N, 5.24%; IR (KBr cm⁻¹) : 3029 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2425 (CH₂ str.), 1787, 1752 (C=O cyclic amide str.), 3320 (NH str.),

829 (Ar-Cl str.), 1614 (C=O str.), 1423 (C-N str.) and 1580 (C=C str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ ppm) : 4.25 (2H, s, CH_2), 2.13 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.24 (1H, s, NH), 7.65 (1H, d, CH), 7.39 (1H, d, CH) and 7.16–8.47 (15H, m, Ar-H).

N-{4-[3-(2-Chlorophenyl)prop-2-enoyl]phenyl}-3-[(1,3-dioxo-1,3-dihydro-2H-isoindol-2-yl)methyl]-4-methylbenzamide (**4d**) : Found : C, 70.05; H, 3.35; N, 4.39. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$: C, 71.84; H, 4.33; N, 5.24%; IR (KBr cm^{-1}) : 3022 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2401 (CH_2 str.), 1772, 1718 (C=O cyclic amide str.), 3312 (NH str.), 833 (Ar-Cl str.), 1615 (C=O str.), 1433 (C-N str.) and 1570 (C=C str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ ppm) : 4.16 (2H, s, CH_2), 2.47 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.33 (1H, s, NH), 7.52 (1H, d, CH), 7.48 (1H, d, CH) and 7.06–8.19 (15H, m, Ar-H).

N-{4-[3-(2-Hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-enoyl]phenyl}-3-[(1,3-dioxo-1,3-dihydro-2H-isoindol-2-yl)methyl]-4-methylbenzamide (**4e**) : Found : C, 72.18; H, 5.12; N, 3.26. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$: C, 74.41; H, 4.68; N, 5.42%; IR (KBr cm^{-1}) : 3031 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2389 (CH_2 str.), 1726, 1711 (C=O cyclic amide str.), 3315 (NH str.), 3591 (O-H str.), 1612 (C=O str.), 1474 (C-N str.) and 1514 (C=C str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ ppm) : 4.10 (2H, s, CH_2), 2.54 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.35 (1H, s, NH), 7.51 (1H, d, CH), 7.45 (1H, d, CH), 3.16 (1H, s, OH) and 7.10–8.15 (15H, m, Ar-H).

N-{4-[3-(2-Hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-enoyl]phenyl}-3-[(1,3-dioxo-1,3-dihydro-2H-isoindol-2-yl)methyl]-4-methylbenzamide (**4f**) : Found : C, 71.18; H, 5.16; N, 3.28. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$: C, 74.41; H, 4.68; N, 5.42%; IR (KBr cm^{-1}) : 3031 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2415 (CH_2 str.), 1762, 1745 (C=O cyclic amide str.), 3332 (NH str.), 3589 (O-H str.), 1632 (C=O str.), 1410 (C-N str.) and 1561 (C=C str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ ppm) : 3.99 (2H, s, CH_2), 2.31 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.12 (1H, s, NH), 7.06 (1H, d, CH), 7.21 (1H, d, CH), 3.18 (1H, s, OH) and 7.11–8.39 (15H, m, Ar-H).

N-{4-[3-(2-Fluorophenyl)prop-2-enoyl]phenyl}-3-[(1,3-dioxo-1,3-dihydro-2H-isoindol-2-yl)methyl]-4-methylbenzamide (**4g**) : Found : C, 71.21; H, 2.74; N, 4.04. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{F}$: C, 74.12; H, 4.47; N, 5.40%; IR (KBr cm^{-1}) : 3026 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2401 (CH_2 str.), 1778, 1725 (C=O cyclic amide str.), 3302 (NH str.), 1182 (C-F str.), 1619 (C=O str.), 1432 (C-N str.) and

1568 (C=C str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ ppm) : 4.12 (2H, s, CH_2), 2.51 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.31 (1H, s, NH), 7.56 (1H, d, CH), 7.45 (1H, d, CH) and 7.02–8.15 (15H, m, Ar-H).

N-{4-[3-(2-Methoxyphenyl)prop-2-enoyl]phenyl}-3-[(1,3-dioxo-1,3-dihydro-2H-isoindol-2-yl)methyl]-4-methylbenzamide (**4h**) : Found : C, 70.15; H, 3.46; N, 3.85. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$: C, 74.70; H, 4.94; N, 5.28%; IR (KBr cm^{-1}) : 3018 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2312 (CH_2 str.), 1762, 1711 (C=O cyclic amide str.), 3323 (NH str.), 1152 (O- CH_3 str.), 1611 (C=O str.), 1401 (C-N str.) and 1546 (C=C str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ ppm) : 4.52 (2H, s, CH_2), 2.12 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.78 (1H, s, NH), 7.31 (1H, d, CH), 7.01 (1H, d, CH), 3.15 (3H, s, O- CH_3) and 7.24–8.01 (15H, m, Ar-H).

N-{4-[3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)prop-2-enoyl]phenyl}-3-[(1,3-dioxo-1,3-dihydro-2H-isoindol-2-yl)methyl]-4-methylbenzamide (**4i**) : Found : C, 70.02; H, 3.64; N, 3.94. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$: C, 74.70; H, 4.94; N, 5.28%; IR (KBr cm^{-1}) : 3020 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2402 (CH_2 str.), 1774, 1720 (C=O cyclic amide str.), 3361 (NH str.), 1178 (O- CH_3 str.), 1676 (C=O str.), 1418 (C-N str.) and 1597 (C=C str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ ppm) : 4.61 (2H, s, CH_2), 2.37 (3H, s, CH_3), 6.02 (1H, s, NH), 7.32 (1H, d, CH), 7.27 (1H, d, CH), 3.34 (3H, s, O- CH_3) and 7.64–8.13 (15H, m, Ar-H).

N-{4-[3-(Furan-2-yl)prop-2-enoyl]phenyl}-3-[(1,3-dioxo-1,3-dihydro-2H-isoindol-2-yl)methyl]-4-methylbenzamide (**4j**) : Found : C, 71.25; H, 3.25; N, 4.17. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$: C, 73.46; H, 4.52; N, 5.71; IR (KBr cm^{-1}) : 3021 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2360 (CH_2 str.), 1720, 1598 (C=O cyclic amide str.), 3393 (NH str.), 1526 (C=O str.), 1460 (C-N str.) and 1598 (C=C str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ ppm) : 4.81 (2H, s, CH_2), 2.17 (3H, s, CH_3), 6.03 (1H, s, NH), 7.39 (1H, d, CH), 7.36 (1H, d, CH) and 7.56–7.94 (14H, m, Ar-H).

Conventional synthesis of N-{4-[3-(substituted phenyl)prop-2-enoyl]phenyl}-3-[(1,3-dioxo-1,3-dihydro-2H-isoindol-2-yl)methyl]-4-methylbenzamide (**4a-j**) :

To a mixture of compound (**3**) (0.01 mol) and substituted aromatic aldehydes (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol, a solution of sodium acetate (0.012 mol) in acetic acid (5 mL) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a heating mantle for 12 h. The reaction mixture was con-

centrated, kept overnight and poured into ice water. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and re-crystallized from ethanol.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the Head, Department of Chemistry, M. L. Sukhadia University, Udaipur for providing laboratory facilities and to the Director, SAIF, CDRI, Lucknow, India for providing spectral and analytical data. Authors are grateful to Antimicrobial Research Laboratory, particularly Dr. Kanika Sharma, Department of Botany, M. L. Sukhadia University for evaluation of antimicrobial activities.

References

1. S. Crosignani, D. Launay, B. Linclau and M. Bradley, *Mol. Diversity*, 2003, **7**, 3.
2. M. S. Schmidt, A. M. Reverdito, L. Kremenchuzky, I. A. Perillo and M. M. Blanco, *Molecules*, 2008, **13**, 831.
3. B. Martin, H. Sektjic and C. Chassaing, *Org. Lett.*, 2003, **5**, 1851.
4. R. Hekmatshoar, M. M. Heravi, B. Baghernejad and K. Asadollah, *Phosphorus, Sulfur Silicon Relat. Elem.*, 2004, **179**, 1611.
5. Y. Li, Y. Wang and J. Wang, *Russ. J. Org. Chem.*, 2008, **44**, 358.
6. J. Fraga-Dubreuil, G. Çomak, A. W. Taylor and M. P. Matlack, *Green Chem.*, 2007, **9**, 1067.
7. M. M. Heravi, R. H. Shoar and L. Pedram, *J. Mol. Catal., A : Chem.*, 2005, **231**, 89.
8. J. F. Zhou, F. X. Zhu, Y. Z. Song and Y. L. Zhu, *Arkivoc*, 2006, **14**, 175.
9. D. A. Heerding, L. T. Christmann, T. J. Clark, D. J. Holmes, S. F. Rittenhouse, D. T. Takata and J. W. Venslavsky, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2003, **13**, 3771.
10. M. M. Mojtahedi, E. Akbarzadeh, R. Sharifi and M. S. Abaee, *Org. Lett.*, 2007, **9**, 2791.
11. D. Prajapati, K. C. Lakhok, J. S. Sandhu and A. C. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **43**, 959
12. W. B. Sun, P. Zhang, J. Fan, S. H. Chen and Z. H. Zhang, *Synth. Commun.*, 2010, **40**, 587
13. A. K. Chakraborti, S. Rudrawar and A. Kondaskar, *Eur. J. Chem.*, 2004, 3597.
14. S. D. Shrivastava and D. K. Shukla, *J. Indian Chem Soc.*, 2008, **85**, 306.
15. B. D. Naik and K. R. Desai, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2004, **16**, 1749.
16. V. Kumar and R. Dhakarey, *J. Indian Council Chem.*, 2003, **20**, 46.
17. D. U. Warad, C. D. Satish, V. H. Kulkarni and C. S. Bajgur, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 415
18. Y. Lingappa, S. S. Rao, R. V. S. S. N. Ravikumari and P. S. Rao, *Radiat. Eff. Defects Solids*, 2007, **162**, 11.
19. V. L. M. Sena, R. M. Shrivastava, R. O. Silva and V. L. M. Lima, *Il Farmaco*, 2003, **58**, 1283.
20. R. M. Shrivastava, F. J. S. Oliveira, L. P. da Silva, J. R. F. Filho, S. P. Oliveira and V. L. M. Lima, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 2001, **332**, 335.
21. T. Wang, Y. H. Zhang, H. Ji, Y. P. Chen and S. X. Peng, *Chin. Chem. Lett.*, 2008, **19**, 26.
22. J. Li, *J. Chem. Cryst.*, 2009, **40**, 428.
23. Z. Soyer, F. S. Kılıç, K. Ero and V. Pabuçcuolu, *Il Farmaco*, 2004, **59**, 595
24. O. Akgul, F. S. Kilic. K. Erol and V. Pabuccuoglu, *Arch. Pharm.*, 2007, **340**, 656.
25. H. S. Patel, H. J. Mistry, N. K. Patel and S. N. Desai, *Bulgerian Chem. Commun.*, 2004, **36**, 167
26. A. Orzeszko, B. Kaminska, G. Orzeszko and B. J. Starosciak, *Farmaco*, 2000, **55**, 619.
27. L. Neung-Ju, L. Su-Jin, K. Seon-hee, K. Young-Soo, M. Seong-bae, S. Honglae, K. Kyung-Tae and T. Emmanuel A., *Eur. Polym. J.*, 2004, **40**, 1291.
28. Y. A. Al-Soud and N. A. Al-Masoudi, *Pharmazie*, 2001, **56**, 372.

